

Level of Hamstring Muscle Flexibility in Yoga Performers in the Yoga Community in Denpasar City

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Abstract

The practice of yoga has experienced significant popularity in the modern era, transforming from a traditional to a global health trend. Pasemetonan Yoga Asana Seger Oger is one of the communities in Bali that emphasizes the practice of yoga as its main focus. In doing yoga, hamstring muscle flexibility is one of the important physical components of performing various asana movements. The purpose of the study was to provide an overview of the level of hamstring muscle flexibility in yoga performers at Pasemetonan Yoga Asana Seger Oger Denpasar City. This descriptive quantitative study involved 97 research subjects selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. The research subjects were taken using a purposive sampling technique. Measurement of hamstring muscle flexibility was measured using the sit and reach test. The results of descriptive statistical tests show the results of the level of flexibility of the hamstring muscles in yoga performers at Pasemetonan Yoga Asana Seger Oger Denpasar City, namely as many as 4 people (4.1%) with fair categories, as many as 5 people (5.2%) with good categories, as many as 23 people (23.7%) with very good categories and as many as 65 people (67%) with excellent categories. This study concludes that most yoga performers at Pasemetonan Yoga Asana Seger Oger Denpasar City have hamstring muscle flexibility in the excellent category. The suggestion of this research is the importance of maintaining hamstring muscle flexibility, by doing yoga activities.

Keywords: flexibility, hamstring muscle, yoga

INTRODUCTION

The practice of yoga has now undergone a significant transformation and popularity in the modern era. In recent decades, yoga has evolved from a traditional practice into a global health and fitness trend. This development is driven by various factors including awareness of its health benefits, both physical, mental, and spiritual, which is also supported by modern society's understanding of the importance of health and changes in lifestyle. In addition, yoga is now easier to access than ever before. Many yoga studios offer classes for various levels, online yoga classes, communities of people who practice yoga, and free video tutorials that are easily available via the Internet.¹

One of the community groups in Bali that emphasizes yoga practice as its main focus is Pasemetonan Seger Oger, Denpasar City.² The manifestation of this

activity is realized in a series of events that are routinely held in the Niti Mandala Renon field or coastal areas in Bali, with a routine schedule every day both in the morning and evening. There is added value to this initiative activity, where this activity is free of charge.

Flexibility is one of the important physical components of doing yoga asana. Flexibility is the body's ability to perform movements with a maximum range of motion in certain joints. In the context of yoga, body flexibility is the main focus because yoga practice can help improve overall body flexibility. An article states that yoga provides significant benefits in terms of increasing body flexibility and overall body balance.³ With a focus on muscle stretching and good breathing, yoga helps in increasing the flexibility of the body, so that individuals who practice yoga can feel more comfortable in various

daily activities and reduce the risk of muscle injuries.

In practicing yoga, hamstring muscle flexibility is very important. Flexible hamstring muscles can help in doing various yoga poses or can affect comfort and ability in poses that involve flexibility in the hip area. A study conducted by LaSala et al., (2021) showed that regular yoga practice can improve hamstring muscle flexibility in healthy individuals.

Increased hamstring flexibility through yoga can also be felt by various age groups, such as research conducted on elderly VIP Fitness Telkom Jabar in 2019, obtained results that there is an effect of yoga on the flexibility of the hip, back, and hamstring joints in middle-aged elderly aged 45-59 years which is indicated by a significance value of $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$), and there is an effect of yoga on the flexibility of the shoulders, hips of elderly aged 59-74 years with a significance value of $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$), which means that yoga can provide increased muscle flexibility in the elderly, one of which is the hamstring muscle.⁵

Good hamstring muscle flexibility, then a person will be able to do various yoga poses properly and correctly, such as the Forward Fold pose (Paschimottanasana), Downward Dog (Adho Mukha Svanasana), and Pigeon Pose (Eka Pada Rajakapotasana) which require hamstring muscle flexibility. In addition, good hamstring muscle flexibility can have a positive impact on health and functional activities of the body, so that a person can work and do activities in everyday life well. However, on the other hand, decreased hamstring muscle flexibility can cause susceptibility to limited movement, postural disorders, and pain in the back of the thigh, and can increase the risk of musculoskeletal injuries.⁶ This is supported by analytical observational research, with a cross-sectional approach that aims to determine

the relationship between hamstring muscle flexibility and lower back pain in women aged 18-22 years. The results of the study showed that there was a relationship between hamstring muscle flexibility and lower back pain in women aged 18-22 years with a p -value=0.000 and a negative correlation direction or a non-unidirectional correlation between hamstring muscle flexibility and lower back pain in women aged 18-22 years.⁷

The increase in muscle flexibility that can be achieved through yoga can vary depending on factors such as age, gender, and the physical condition of the individual. However, stretching exercises that are also contained in yoga asana, if done well and correctly will provide benefits for physical fitness, one of which is increased body flexibility. Therefore, it is important to consult a professional yoga instructor before starting a yoga program to ensure that the program is appropriate for the individual's physical condition and goals.

A professional yoga instructor is someone who has practiced yoga intensively and regularly, has in-depth knowledge of yoga, and can teach yoga to others. Professional yoga instructors have undergone yoga training and certification and can teach various types of yoga with varying levels of difficulty. In conducting yoga training, a professional yoga instructor should adopt an approach that is specific and tailored to the physical condition of each individual. A careful study of body flexibility, one of which is hamstring muscle flexibility, is key to designing an optimal and progressive exercise program. This variation in flexibility levels can affect the implementation of yoga movements, and therefore, individual assessment of each participant is important. Professional yoga instructors need to understand that each participant can have different exercise needs, depending on their level of flexibility. Therefore, designing an

exercise program that can be adjusted and accommodates variations in hamstring flexibility is a wise strategy. A progressive program can also provide support for the gradual development of participant flexibility over time. By combining a deep understanding of each individual's physical characteristics, yoga instructors can provide a more effective and safe exercise experience.

However, until now, there has been no empirical study that presents data on the level of hamstring muscle flexibility that can be accessed at the place of yoga practice in the Seger Oger yoga asana session. So far, the research that has been done has focused on the psychological impact of yoga practice, one of which is the level of depression.² The existence of data on the level of hamstring muscle flexibility is essential, considering the importance of this data in enabling a yoga instructor to design a specific and progressive flexibility training program, which can be adjusted to the needs of each individual and ensure that yoga participants can practice yoga safely.

METHOD

This research was conducted at Pasemetonan Yoga Asana Seger Oger, Denpasar City. Data collection for the

study was carried out in June-August 2024. This study involved 97 research subjects selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. This study uses a purposive sampling technique for selecting research subjects. This method is by the researcher's desire to obtain subjects who meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria intentionally, namely, participants are members of Pasemetonan Yoga Asana Seger Oger, Denpasar City who have actively participated in routine yoga activities for at least the last 3 months and are not involved in other physical activities besides yoga. Measurement of hamstring muscle flexibility was measured using the sit and reach test. The results of the sit and reach test measurements obtained were then interpreted by being categorized or grouped according to the existing levels, namely need improvement, fair, good, very good, and excellent.

RESULT

The data of 97 research subjects with an age range of 30-69 years were analyzed to obtain descriptive research statistics which can be seen in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1. Level of Hamstring Flexibility

Level of Hamstring Flexibility	Frequency	Percentage
Fair	4	4,1%
Good	5	5,2%
Very Good	23	23,7%
Excellent	65	67,0%

Figure 1. Level of hamstring muscle flexibility in yoga performers.

DISCUSSION

Yoga is a practice that is widely recognized for its benefits in improving flexibility, strength, and general well-being. One specific area that is often focused on in yoga is hamstring flexibility. Hamstring flexibility is essential for muscle health and lower body mobility, and can minimize the risk of injury.⁴ The results of this study showed that most yoga performers (67%) showed excellent flexibility levels, while 23.7% had very good flexibility levels and only 9.3% of participants showed lower levels of flexibility (good or fair).

This study is in line with previous findings showing that consistent yoga practice can improve muscle flexibility, including the hamstring muscles. According to a study by Luo & Huang, 2023 regular yoga practice can significantly improve flexibility and range of motion in the muscles of the body, including the hamstrings. Other studies also support this finding by showing that yoga practice improves muscle flexibility through the repetition of specific stretches and postures.^{4,9} These results are also consistent with research by Chapman-Lopez et al., 2023 which showed that dynamic and static stretching, as performed in yoga, is effective in

increasing muscle length and flexibility. Thus, yoga practice is an effective intervention to improve hamstring muscle flexibility, which may contribute to reduced injury risk and increased mobility.¹⁰

Increased muscle flexibility is one of the main benefits of yoga practice, which is the result of various physiological and biomechanical mechanisms. Increased muscle flexibility, including the hamstring muscles, is related to changes in the structure and function of muscle tissue and neuromuscular adaptations. In doing yoga, it will involve various types of stretching, both static and dynamic. This stretching contributes to increased flexibility by increasing the length of the muscles and surrounding connective tissues.¹⁰ During stretching, collagen fibers in connective tissues, such as tendons and fascia, are stretched, which allows them to lengthen better.¹⁰

Connective tissues such as tendons and fascia are made up of collagen and elastin fibers. Yoga exercises that involve repeated stretching can modify the structure of collagen fibers by increasing elasticity and reducing muscle stiffness. This process causes collagen to become more flexible and elastic after consistent stretching exercises. Yoga exercises can reduce muscle stiffness by increasing muscle relaxation and increasing elastin production. This is due to decreased resistance to stretching and increased muscle capacity to stretch further without experiencing excessive tension.¹¹

Muscle stretching during yoga affects the myotatic reflex or stretch reflex which functions to maintain muscle length and protect against damage. Yoga practice can reduce the activity of this reflex, allowing the muscles to stretch further without experiencing excessive contraction.⁹ The viscoelastic response of muscles, tendons, ligaments, fascia, and joints to slow stretching exercises in doing yoga poses can result in less muscle

tension, compared to stretching procedures that are done quickly or the faster the stretching, the higher the stiffness that occurs in the muscles.¹¹ Yoga practice can also affect the central nervous system by increasing body awareness and neuromuscular control. This allows individuals to stretch more efficiently and reduce muscle tension through better relaxation.¹¹

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that most yoga performers at Pasemetonan Yoga Asana Seger Oger Denpasar City have hamstring muscle flexibility in the excellent category. The suggestion from this study is the importance of maintaining hamstring muscle flexibility, by doing yoga activities regularly, with good muscle flexibility a person can move freely and can minimize the occurrence of injury.

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